

Common Circumstances Before Suicide Involving Firearms Among Black American Adults: Understanding the Challenges as Primary Care Providers

For Black adult patients, the following might occur:

WORSENING MENTAL OR PHYSICAL HEALTH

Increased symptoms in mental or physical health conditions. Mental health conditions might include depression and anxiety. Physical health conditions might include pain, cancer, and chronic illnesses (like diabetes).

Individuals who have health conditions might stop treatment before suicide.

RELATIONSHIP PROBLEMS & FREQUENT ARGUMENTS WITH LOVED ONES

Worsening romantic relationships due to infidelity or breakup, causing anger, sorrow, and grief.

Intense arguments might be common before a suicide attempt.

ALCOHOL AND SUBSTANCE USE

Alcohol and other substances might be used before a suicide attempt to help cope with life stresses.

FINANCIAL AND LEGAL DIFFICULTIES

Recent job loss, not being hired for a job, or needing to work multiple jobs to make ends meet.

Cannot pay mortgage or rent, experiencing homelessness, losing a vehicle, or owing money.

Legal difficulties such as court hearings or previous arrests, often with financial difficulties.

ACCESSIBLE FIREARMS

Different types of firearms might be purchased legally or illegally before suicide. Firearms might be stolen or borrowed from friends, romantic partners, or family members before suicide. Handguns are very common.

Firearms might be unsafely stored or unlocked in the home. But safe firearm storage is still common before suicide (like using a gun safe or lock).

When someone is experiencing suicidal thoughts, it might be difficult to voluntarily limit their firearm access because they may want to keep their firearms close for protection or their constitutional right to bear arms.

Primary care providers and workers play important roles in suicide prevention. A previous study found that about **83% of individuals who died by suicide used health care services within the year prior to their death — and over half had contact with a primary care provider.**¹ This is why it is important for primary care providers to understand specific challenges that their patients may face.

Most suicide deaths involve firearms,² and **rates of suicide using firearms have been rising among Black American adults.**³ Our recent study summarized the personal challenges Black adults often experience before dying by firearm suicide (shown on the left side of this page).⁴

Additionally, primary care providers face specific barriers that may make it difficult to implement suicide prevention strategies in their practice, including:

- **Distrust of Healthcare Providers by Patients Who Identify as Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC)**
 - Distrust of healthcare providers is common within BIPOC communities, especially among Black and Latino/a persons, due to repeated medical mistreatment and malpractice.⁵
- **Difficulty Finding the Language to Talk about Suicide and Firearms**
 - Some providers find it difficult to ask if someone feels suicidal and may need extra help on how to bring up the conversation about suicidality or counsel their patients on lethal means safety.⁶
- **Providers' Mental Health, Self-Care, and Wellbeing**
 - Physicians are prone to experiencing mental health stigma themselves and report concerns about reputation and confidentiality as barriers to seeking treatment.⁶

Knowing the challenges Black Americans experience can help save lives in our community. But this is not enough. We must also address the barriers that make it difficult to implement suicide prevention strategies or talk about firearm safety in primary care settings.

Scan the following QR code for more information about:

- **Warning signs.** Suicide warning signs include talking about, planning (such as random goodbye texts, calls, notes, and giving away sentimental items), or researching ways to die.
- **Counseling on Access to Lethal Means (CALM).** Creating space and time between a firearm and someone having suicidal thoughts can save a life.⁷ **Free training** is available to help you discuss lethal means safety with your patients.
- **Implementation Toolkit for Primary Care Practices.** Access a **free toolkit** with information and training on suicide epidemiology, implementing suicide prevention practices, reimbursement, Safety Plan templates, clinician self-care, and more.

